

EVAPORATION AND WIND ABOVE A METHANE LAKE ON TITAN

FROM A NEW 3D MESOSCALE MODEL

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Starting point: the mtWRF model

Research Paper

Air-sea interactions on titan: Lake evaporation, atmospheric circulation, and cloud formation

Scot C.R. Rafkin^{*}, Alejandro Soto

Icarus 2020

Implementation of a radiation scheme

Schneider et al 2012 (gray scheme)
Tomasko et al 2008 (Huygens/DISR)

Implementation of a radiation scheme

☰ Schneider et al 2012 (gray scheme)
Tomasko et al 2008 (Huygens/DISR)

Same general solution
+ new energy fluxes (solar and IR)
+ new diurnal variations of all variables
=> radiation cannot be neglected!

☰ Chatain et al, PSJ, 2022

Moving to 3D!

Sea breeze from lake to land at the surface

Subsidence over the cold lake

Effect of divergence: 2D vs 3D

3D equivalent of 2D simulations

3D

Effect of divergence: 2D vs 3D

2D

3D

⇒ sea breeze less extended over land in 3D

Effect of convergence: 2D vs 3D

2D

3D

⇒ subsidence over the lake stronger in 3D

Methane

2D

3D

⇒ more methane evaporation

⇒ but also more diffusion in 3D

⇒ less methane vapor accumulation over the lake

Temperature

2D

3D

AIR:

less moist cold
air accumulation
⇒ warmer air

SURFACE:

more
evaporation
⇒ colder lake

Effect of shoreline

effect of concavity

interactions between lakes

⇒ local intensification of wind & evaporation

Effect of shoreline

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interactions between lakes

⇒ local intensification of wind & evaporation

Summary: effects of 3D divergence and irregular shoreline

- Moving from 2D to 3D affects the circulation:
 - sea breeze less extended over land
 - stronger downwelling above the lake
- It has many repercussions:
 - more efficient diffusion of the cold moist air towards the land
 - stronger evaporation, enhanced cooling of the lake
- Effect of the shoreline: local intensification of the wind & evaporation

Perspectives: - add the topography of the rims
- use wetlands instead of dry land